

Impact of Quantitative Visualization and Image Processing on the Study of Small- Scale Air-Sea Interaction

Bernd Jähne

Interdisciplinary Center for Scientific Computing, University of Heidelberg
Im Neuenheimer Feld 368, 69120 Heidelberg, Germany
Scripps Institution of Oceanography, Physical Oceanography Res. Div.
La Jolla, CA 92093-0230, USA
email: bjaehne@ucsd.edu

Abstract

Non-intrusive image measuring methods based on modern photonics and digital image processing techniques provide and continue to provide an unprecedented quantitative insight into small-scale air-sea interaction processes.

1 Introduction

From the early beginnings, scientists tried to record their observations in pictures. In early times, they could do this only in the form of drawings. Remarkable examples are known, for instance, from Leonardo da Vinci. Any visual observation, however, was limited to the capabilities of the human eye. The invention of photography triggered the first revolution in the usage of images for science and extended the possibilities for visual observation to non-visible radiation such as ultraviolet light, X-rays, and various particulate radiation. However, the cumbersome manual evaluation of photographs restricted the quantitative analysis. Nowadays, we experience a second revolution of scientific imaging. Images can be converted into electronic form, digital images, that are analyzed quantitatively using computers to perform exact measurements.

In this paper, we discuss the impact of these techniques for the experimental investigation of small-scale air-sea interactions. These processes are a key example for the application of imaging techniques in two respects. First, large scale processes become visible in aerial and satellite images by their interaction with small-scale processes that themselves cannot be resolved in the images but influence the imaging mechanism. A classical example are *sun glitter* images (Figure 1). The brightness of the sun glitter is directly related to the two-dimensional wave slope distribution which to a large extend is influenced by short wind waves. These short wind waves are modulated by slicks, swell, internal waves, tidal currents, etc. In this way, these phenomena become visible in sun glitter images as well as in

Figure 1: Sun glitter image from coastal Pacific waters taken on a flight from Los Angeles to San Diego by the author. It shows the variation of the micro-surface roughness constituted by gravity/capillary waves by slicks, swell, and internal waves. (For color figure, see Plate 1.)

synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images. Second, the boundary layers at the wavy ocean surface are very difficult to investigate by conventional intrusive probes. This is especially true for air-sea gas transfer. The thin aqueous mass boundary layer which is at most a few $100\ \mu\text{m}$ thick can hardly be profiled by any intrusive probe, especially under field conditions.

Therefore, all conventional techniques do not take any measurements in aqueous mass boundary layer that controls air-sea gas transfer. Based on mass balance methods, they only measure the mean flux through the aqueous mass boundary layer integrated over large temporal (hours to days) and spatial scales. It is obvious that no direct insight into the mechanisms of air-sea gas exchange can be gained in this way. At best, an empirical parameterization can be obtained.

The plan of this review paper is to give a brief summary of the current state of the art of imaging techniques that are of importance for an experimental investigation of small-scale air-sea interaction processes with emphasize on air-sea gas exchange (*section 2*). Based on the expected developments in photonics and digital image processing one the one hand, and the experimental data needed mostly for a better understanding of small-scale air sea interaction processes one the other hand, we discuss the imaging techniques that can be envisioned to be developed within the next five years (*section 3*).

Figure 2: Wave slope images taken in the large IMST wind/wave flume, University of Marseille, at 4.6 m fetch and 4 m/s wind speed. The sector shown is about $0.4 \times 0.4 \text{ m}^2$. The wind is blowing from the left to the right. Slope color key: white means a flat surface, from yellow to red the slope is increasing into wind direction, from green to blue against the wind direction. From Jähne [1985]. (For color figure, see Plate 2.)

2 State of the Art

In recent years, tremendous progress has been made with imaging measuring techniques that take spatially resolved measurements of various key parameters involved in small-scale air-sea interaction.

2.1 Imaging of Short Wind Waves

The foundation for optical techniques to measure short waves was laid by the pioneering work of Cox. He not only used sun glitter images to infer the wave slope distribution and *mean square slope* [Cox and Munk, 1954], but also introduced the usage of optical techniques based on light refraction for the measurement of *wave slope* [Cox, 1958]. Keller and Gotwols [1983] were the first to use refractive optical techniques to capture wave slope images.

Figures 2 and 3 show some of the first wave slope images taken by the author in the Marseille wind/wave flume in 1984; Figures 4 and 5 illustrate the equipment used later in this facility by the author. Jähne and Riemer [1990] conducted the first systematic study of 2-D wave number spectra of short wind waves from the Delft wind/wave flume. The first spatial wave slope measurements taken at sea are reported in this volume [Klinke and Jähne, 1995]. The two most promising techniques used nowadays both in the field and laboratory are the *Scanning Laser Slope Gauge* (SLSG) [Bock et al., 1995; Hwang, 1995] and the *Imaging Slope Gauge* (ISG) [Klinke and Jähne, 1995]. A detailed comparative study of optical wave imaging techniques can

Figure 3: As Figure 2 at **a** 6.3 m/s and **b** 8 m/s wind speed. From Jähne [1985]. (For color figure, see Plate 3.)

Figure 4: Wave slope visualization system used by the author in the large wind/wave flume of the IMST, University of Marseille. A large screen close to the ceiling is illuminated from aside by two rows of lamps (see Figure 5) to produce an intensity wedge in wind direction. In this way, the along-wind wave slope can be made visible. Through the plane water surface, the submerged optical parts can be seen. In order to increase the distance of the camera to the water surface, the optical path is folded two times by mirrors. Slope calibration is — as shown in the figure — performed by using an artificial wave consisting of a Perspex foil bent by a frame into a sinusoidal shape. The whole system is mounted onto a carriage so that it can be moved through the facility. (For color figure, see Plate 4.)

Figure 5: Wave slope visualization system in operation at high wind speeds in the large wind/wave flume of the IMST, University of Marseille, France. The system is viewed through one of the large glass windows of the facility. In the upper right corner, some of the lamps can be seen used to illuminate the large screen. (For color figure, see Plate 5.)

be found in Jähne *et al.* [1994].

2.2 Imaging of Flow Fields Close to the Water Surface

Flow visualization techniques are as old as experimental studies in hydrodynamics but quantitative techniques such as *Particle Imaging Velocimetry (PIV)* and *Particle Tracking Velocimetry (PTV)* became available only recently. The many papers published in this volume indicate that this field is meanwhile well established [Banner and Peirson, 1995; Cowen *et al.*, 1995; Dieter *et al.*, 1995; Etoh and Takehara, 1995; Gulliver and Tamburrino, 1995; Hering *et al.*, 1995] and that the spatial resolution is sufficient to perform even measurements within the aqueous viscous boundary layer.

2.3 Imaging of Bubbles

Besides acoustic techniques, optical techniques are widely used to measure *bubble size distributions*. This volume contains the works of De Leeuw and Cohen [1995], Geißler and Jähne [1995], and Loewen *et al.* [1995]. Optical bubble concentration measurements have also been used in the WABEX'93 experiment [Asher *et al.*, 1995].

2.4 Thermal Imaging

Infrared imaging provides very promising opportunities to gain more insight into small-scale air-sea interaction processes. *Jessup et al.* [1995] study the skin layer recovery rate, while *Haußecker et al.* [1995] and *Haußecker and Jähne* [1995] report first in situ measurements of the air-sea gas exchange rate using heat as a proxy tracer. The *heat flux* at the ocean surface can be inferred from temperature gradient measurements using infrared spectral radiometry [McKeown, 1995].

2.5 Imaging of Concentration Fields of Dissolved Gases

Almost 30 years ago, *Hiby* [1968] used acid and alkaline gases and fluorescent pH indicators to investigate the transport mechanisms in falling films. He demonstrated that both mean and fluctuating concentrations can be measured successfully. Similar techniques have successfully been transferred to wind/wave tunnel studies (see Figure 6). Today, two techniques are available to perform high-resolution *concentration field* measurements within the aqueous mass boundary layer: *quenching* of the fluorescence of *PBA* by dissolved oxygen [Duke and Hanratty, 1995] and the fluorescent pH indicator method [Münsterer et al., 1995].

3 Envisioned Imaging Techniques

Still some key parameters cannot be measured and remain a challenge for future instrumentation development. Here a prediction is given what key quantities might be within the reach of novel techniques until the turn of the century.

3.1 Local Measurements of the Gas Transfer Rate

Although the controlled flux technique using heat as a proxy tracer (see above) does not only provide fast local measurements of the transfer rate but also gives direct insight into the mechanisms by taking images of the surface, it has the disadvantage that the Prandtl number (around 7) is about two decades lower than the Schmidt number for dissolved gas tracers (400 - 1000). Therefore, the development of similar techniques as the controlled flux technique but with a tracer of higher Schmidt number is very desirable.

3.2 Measurements of the Wind Stress at the Water Surface

One of the key problems to understand the mechanisms of air-sea gas transfer is the lacking knowledge of the spatial and temporal distribution of *wind stress* at a wavy water surface. More than twenty years ago, *Braun et al.* [1971] used it to measure the surface velocity in falling films. If techniques

Figure 6: Visualization of the mass boundary layer in the large circular wind/wave flume at Heidelberg University. Shown is an image sector of about $0.12 \times 0.17 \text{ m}^2$ at the water surface viewed from above. The mass boundary is made visible by absorbing NH_3 gas in a 10^{-3} molar HCl solution. Absorption of NH_3 gas makes the mass boundary layer alkaline. This alkaline layer is made visible by the fluorescent pH indicator fluorescein. Therefore, the brightness in the image is directly proportional to the instantaneous thickness of the mass boundary layer. From Jähne [1991]. (For color figure, see Plate 6.)

became available to measure the velocity in different short distances from the surface, a direct determination of the wind stress from the velocity gradient at the water surface would be feasible.

3.3 3-D Imaging of Flow Fields at the Wavy Water Surface

Currently, the flow field can — except for very slow flows — only be taken in 2-D cross sections. With faster imaging sensors utilizing parallel outputs and compact laser-diode pumped solid state lasers, it can be expected that 3-D flow fields may become feasible soon. Other techniques might include

Figure 7: Schematics of a setup recently used by the author's research group [Haußecker and Beyer] in the Delft wind/wave flume to image simultaneously and at the same footprint the wind/wave slope using an imaging slope gauge, and the surface micro turbulence using an active thermal technique. With the latter technique, the water surface is heated up with two infrared radiators and the resulting temperature patterns — reflecting the spatial turbulence structure at the water surface — is observed by an infrared camera. (For color figure, see Plate 7.)

multi-camera setups using photogrammetric techniques to measure 3-D positions or colored light illumination systems.

3.4 3-D Imaging of Concentration Fields

Once measuring techniques for fast scanning of volumes are available for flow measurements, it is only a small step to measure 3-D concentration fields. The real challenge is the required high spatial resolution of better than $10\ \mu\text{m}$ for measurements within the mass boundary layer. At higher wind speeds/wave heights, sophisticated optical wave followers will be required.

3.5 Synoptic Imaging

Of most importance are simultaneous imaging measurements of flow fields, concentration fields, and short wind waves. Simultaneous measurements of flow and concentration provide a direct way to measure fluxes by cross-correlation. An experimental setup for simultaneous measurements of wave slope and surface turbulence is shown in Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 8: Example of a composite image taken with the setup shown in Figure 7. The wave slope is shown in blue, and the water surface temperature in red colors. The image sector is about $0.14 \times 0.20 \text{ m}^2$. (For color figure, see Plate 8.)

4 Conclusions

If only a few of the envisioned techniques become reality, they will have a significant impact on the understanding of small-scale air-sea interaction processes. It is obvious, however, that further development in this area critically depends on our ability to perform interdisciplinary research crossing the boundaries between classical research areas.

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